

Can a sentence of imprisonment imposed in protection of the financial interests of the EU be unlawful? Lessons learned from a court decision rendered following an OLAF report in the scope of the CAP

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Abstract

La protection des intérêts financiers de l'Union européenne et la coopération appropriée des États membres avec l'OLAF sont particulièrement importantes dans le cadre de l'application de la PAC. En ce qui concerne les subventions versées dans le cadre de la politique agricole commune, la protection des intérêts financiers de l'UE est également considérée comme une priorité dans la jurisprudence de la CJUE. La recherche de cet objectif, dans des circonstances spécifiques, peut même l'emporter sur la protection des droits fondamentaux exigée par les principes généraux du droit de l'UE. Outre les règlements visant à protéger les intérêts financiers de l'UE, les règlements relatifs aux subventions exigent également que les États membres garantissent l'utilisation efficace des subventions et prennent des mesures appropriées pour lutter contre les infractions financières. Nous examinerons la jurisprudence de la CJCE en la matière, le rôle des principes généraux du droit de l'UE, l'effet juridique des rapports de l'OLAF et la jurisprudence des tribunaux hongrois en la matière. Enfin, nous présenterons un cas concret et l'évaluerons à la lumière de la jurisprudence de la CJCE.

Der Schutz der finanziellen Interessen der Europäischen Union und eine angemessene Zusammenarbeit der Mitgliedstaaten mit dem OLAF werden im Anwendungsbereich der GAP besonders hervorgehoben. In Bezug auf Subventionen, die im Rahmen der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik bezahlt werden, wird der Schutz der finanziellen Interessen der EU auch in der Rechtsprechung des EuGH als vorrangig angesehen. Das Bestreben, dieses Ziel zu erreichen, kann unter bestimmten Umständen sogar den von den allgemeinen Grundsätzen des EU-Rechts geforderten Schutz der Grundrechte überwiegen. Neben den Regelungen zum Schutz der finanziellen Interessen der EU verlangen die einschlägigen Subventionsverordnungen auch, dass die Mitgliedstaaten die effiziente Verwendung der Subventionen gewährleisten und geeignete Maßnahmen zur Bekämpfung von Finanzdelikten ergreifen. Vorliegend soll diesbezüglich die einschlägige Rechtsprechung des EuGH, die Rolle der allgemeinen Grundsätze des EU-Rechts, die Rechtswirkung der OLAF-Berichte und die einschlägige Rechtsprechung ungarischer Gerichte untersucht werden. Abschließend stellen wir einen konkreten Fall vor und bewerten ihn im Lichte der Rechtsprechung des EuGH.

1. Introduction

The protection of the financial interests of the European Union and appropriate cooperation of the Member States with OLAF are particularly emphatic in the scope of the application of the CAP. In relation to subsidies paid under the Common Agricultural Policy, the protection of financial interests of the EU is also considered a priority in the case-law of the CJEU. The endeavour to achieve that goal, under specific circumstances, may even outweigh the protection of fundamental rights required by the general principles of EU law. In addition to the regulations aimed at protecting the financial interests of the EU, the relevant subsidy regulations also require that the Member States guarantee the efficient use of the subsidies and take appropriate measures to combat financial offences.

In the case of irregularities that harm the financial interests of the EU, the Member States can expect severe financial sanctions, that is, the European Commission can oblige the Member States to bear the financial consequences. OLAF has a role not only in investigating financial irregularities but also in relation to the sanctions imposed on Member States.

The question arises whether, despite of the EU rules protecting the financial interests of the European Union, a ruling of a national court, which, following an OLAF report, imposes imprisonment to be served for fraud related to land-based subsidies may be contrary to EU law?

To answer that question, we will review the relevant case-law of the CJEU, the role of the general principles of EU law, the legal effect of the OLAF reports, and the relevant case-law of Hungarian courts. Lastly, we present a specific case and assess it in the light of the case-law of the CJEU.

2. The different role of the general principles of the EU law in the scope of the application of the CAP

According to Denys Simon,¹ the general principles of the EU law are unwritten norms,² established by the case-law of the CJEU on the basis of “common values”³ that characterize a given legal order. Joel Rideau argues that the general principles are the unwritten sources of EU law, which can be considered the “creative products” of the CJEU.⁴ In Lamprini Xenou’s⁵ opinion, the CJEU does not intend to accurately systematize the content of the general principles in order to maintain a certain flexibility

¹ Denys Simon: Y a-t-il des principes généraux du droit communautaire? *Revue française de théorie juridique*, 14. (1991), 73.

² The general principles of EU law applied by the CJEU are indeed not included in the founding treaties or secondary EU legal acts, however the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union has codified many general principles, so in some cases the CJEU applies a provision of the Charter and a general principle side by side.

³ In its case-law, the CJEU prefers to refer to the common constitutional traditions of the Member States, but this would not be practicable to implement, and there are principles that are meant to ensure the specific conditions of the EU legal order, which, thus, cannot originate from the common constitutional traditions of the member states either.

⁴ Joël Rideau: *Ordre juridique de L’Union européenne - Sources non écrites. JurisClasseur Europe*, 8. (2014), 191.

⁵ Lamprini Xenou: *Les principes généraux du droit de L’Union européenne et la jurisprudence administrative française*. These. 2014.

at their application.⁶ In any case, there is consensus in the legal literature on that the general principles, to a certain extent, “may also be considered superlegalities”,⁷ which means that they are to be observed by both the EU institutions and the Member States.⁸

The objectives of the Common Agricultural Policy is set forth in Article 39 of the TFEU: to promote the standard of living of the agricultural community, to stabilize markets, to assure the availability of supplies, and to ensure that supplies reach consumer at reasonable prices. These objectives are in part of economic, and in part of social nature, and, after reaching a certain level, can only be asserted in conflict with one another.⁹

These objectives are also legally binding, but only the EU legislature may determine which of them become a temporary priority and what measures are to be used to achieve that.¹⁰

Based on the case-law of the CJEU, the EU legislature has a wide margin of political discretion, and a secondary EU act may only be reviewed in the event of the abuse of power or if the given act is clearly unsuitable for achieving the intended objectives.¹¹

In this paper, instead of examining the legal binding force of the objectives of the Common Agricultural Policy or the interrelations of those objectives, but we will analyse what principles are applied in the case of irregularities occurring in relation to the amounts paid under the CAP.

In our viewpoint, basically two types of cases can be distinguished among those irregularities occurring in the Member States in relation to payments under the CAP where the protection of the strict financial interests of the EU arises, or where the applicability of the general principles in favour of the agricultural community or the economic operators is possible.

In the cases that belong to the first type, the Member States apply EU regulations directly, and in the event of an irregularity, the general principles that protect individuals cannot be successfully invoked against the provisions that emphatically protect the financial interests of the EU and impose deterrent sanctions. As it was said above, the EU legislator has a wide margin of discretion regarding the application of the CAP, which allows for a CJEU review in a very limited scope.

As regards the second type of cases, the EU regulation provides a certain margin of discretion to the Member States, allowing for or even requiring implementing measures.

In these cases, the case-law of the CJEU focuses particularly on that the applied national measures must comply with the requirements of the general principles of EU law. Not only the national legislation can be considered as such measure, but individual decisions must also be in conformity with the general principles of EU law. In this field, the case-law of the CJEU prioritizes the general principles protecting individuals against the Member States, while the protection of the financial interests of the EU is somewhat pushed into the background.

⁶ Advocate General’s Opinion C-101/08.

⁷ Denys Simon: *Le système juridique communautaire*. Paris, PUF, 2003. 126.

⁸ The Member States are obliged to observe the general principles of the EU law when they implement EU law.

⁹ Daniele Bianchi: *La politique agricole commune (PAC)*. 2nd edition. Bruxelles, Bruylant, 2012. 51.

¹⁰ Bianchi (2012) op. cit. 52.

¹¹ Bianchi (2012) op. cit. 53.

These latter cases turned out to be the sources of several practical difficulties in national case-law, as the Member States tend to prioritize the financial interests of the EU.¹² In the following, we will review the case-law of the CJEU in relation to these two types of cases.

Among the cases where the EU law is applicable directly, the judgement rendered in the National Farmers' Union case should be mentioned.¹³ The area indicated by the concerned agricultural producer in terms of the agricultural land used by him exceeded the area actually used by him at the submission of the application for subsidy by 20%. The authorities imposed severe sanctions against the concerned agricultural producer in the application of the EU regulation.¹⁴ The question referred to the CJEU concerned the conformity of the imposed sanction with the general principles of the EU law, such as the principles of proportionality, legal certainty, and equal treatment. The CJEU justified the non-assertion of the requirements related to the general principles mainly by taking action against fraud.

Regarding the judgement rendered in the Hofmeister case,¹⁵ the concerned economic operator disputed the application of deterrent sanctions applied in connection with the export refund of certain products, on the grounds the general principles of EU law. The economic operator conducting the export mainly referred to the principles of proportionality¹⁶ and non-discrimination, and with regard to the latter, he particularly emphasized that, in the case of applying sanctions, the regulation does not differentiate between offences committed intentionally and due to negligence. Therefore, according to the interpretation of the concerned economic operator, it does not comply with the general principle of equal treatment, which requires comparable situations to be treated in the same way and different situations differently. The fact that similar deterrent sanctions are to be applied to offences committed intentionally and due to negligence, does not meet the criteria set by the general principle of equal treatment. In essence, the CJEU did not refute that the measure in question does not meet the requirements imposed by the general principles at issue, but it considered that the concerned measures are necessary to protect the financial interests of the EU. The CJEU also mentioned the wide scope of discretion of the EU legislator in the scope of the application of the CAP, which the CJEU can review only under extraordinary circumstances.

With regard to the implementation by Member States, that is, the second type of cases under our examination, the judgement rendered by the CJEU in the Gorje case¹⁷ should be mentioned: a Slovenian commune submitted an application for support for settlement development, which was approved by the paying agency of the concerned Member State. After that, it was established that the works related to the refurbishment of the property at issue were started before the positive decision regarding the application. It should be noted that it is not contrary to EU law to specify that only works carried out after a positive decision on the tender can be supported.

¹² In the case of Hungary, several cases from this category have been referred to the CJEU, but the national case-law seems to have difficulties following the case-law of the CJEU. This will be discussed in detail below.

¹³ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-354/95.

¹⁴ Article 9 of Regulation (EEC) 3887/92.

¹⁵ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-210/00.

¹⁶ The economic operator also relied on the principle of proportionality, which requires that the applied measures do not exceed the extent necessary for achieving the set objectives. According to him, a punishment significantly less severe than the deterrent sanction would have been sufficient to achieve the set goal.

¹⁷ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-111/15.

However, a decision that refuses to pay the full amount of support or reclaims it is incompatible with the criteria established by the general principle of proportionality.¹⁸ It is clear that the protection of the financial interests of the EU, at least compared to the cases discussed above, has been pushed into the background here.

The judgements rendered in the Szemerei case¹⁹ and the Pontini case analysed below also substantiates the fact that the general principles protecting individuals against Member States are prioritized regarding the second type of cases, that is, implementation by Member States. The examination of the latter judgment is also relevant in the sense that, in the analysed example, its adoption into Hungarian case-law played a major role.

3. The adoption of the erroneous judgement rendered in the Pontini case into the Hungarian case-law

The judgment of the CJEU rendered in the Pontini case²⁰ can be considered an important milestone in terms of the Member States' margin of discretion regarding implementation. In the main proceedings, criminal proceedings were initiated against the concerned agricultural producer for serious and sustained fraud to the detriment of the budget of the European Community. Based on the relevant legislation, the livestock aid at issue could be disbursed, inter alia, on the condition that the persons concerned had a suitable area of land at their disposal.

Regarding the land, the agricultural producers involved in the case submitted fictitious contracts when submitting their subsidy applications. One of the most important questions of the preliminary ruling procedure was whether the obligation introduced in national legislation, according to which the right to use the forage areas related to the livestock at issue must be accompanied by a valid legal title, is compatible with the relevant EU provisions.²¹

According to the point of view of the agricultural producers affected by the procedure,²² it is contrary to the spirit of the EU regulations to require a valid legal title defined by the national legislation, because the relevant EU rules only require the use and enjoyment of the affected areas. On the other hand, according to the argument of the Italian government, checking the regularity of EU payments is a Member State obligation defined by the EU legal order. According to the Italian government, requiring proof of legal title contributes to the fulfilment of this Member State obligation.²³

Taking into account the EU provisions for the given area, the CJEU came to the conclusion that the provision of the subsidies at issue should be determined based on the size of the concerned agricultural area and the number of animals kept on it, and not on the basis of a document related to a valid legal

¹⁸ The principle of proportionality required that the measures implied do not exceed what is necessary to achieve the goal: that is, only payments related to the work performed before a positive decision on the tender can be denied or reclaimed lawfully.

¹⁹ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-330/14.

²⁰ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-375/08.

²¹ It should be noted that some of the parties involved contested the falsification of lease agreements, but the CJEU does not have jurisdiction over the facts determined by the national courts.

²² Court of Justice of the European Union, C-375/08, paragraph 53.

²³ *ibid.* paragraphs 55-56.

title certifying the utilization of the areas.²⁴ One of the most important objectives of EU regulations for the area is to halt the trend towards intensification of beef production. In order to achieve the objectives of the regulation, it is not necessary to submit the document related to the legal title, but to prove the actual use, thus the condition of the support is the actual utilization.²⁵

After that,²⁶ the Court examined the concerned condition set forth in national legislation in that regard: the "nature and objectives" of the integrated administration and control system, as well as the extent of discretion accorded to the Member States in relation to implementation in the case examined.²⁷

Based on the relevant EU regulations, within the framework of the integrated administration and control system, the use of EU subsidies must be effectively monitored, and – where appropriate – sanction provisions²⁸ must be established²⁹ in relation to the protection of the Union's financial interests and the regularity of payments under the CAP, in which Member States have discretion.³⁰

The relevant EU regulations specify that the subsidy application must include all necessary information, including those required by the relevant EU regulations and the national legislation.³¹ The relevant EU regulation³² provides the Member States with a margin of discretion in terms of the inspection: inter alia, they must ensure the identification of individual parcels, the rejection of subsidy applications that are contrary to the objectives of the support system,³³ and the protection of the financial interests of the EU.

In the interpretation of the EU court, the relevant EU regulations provide the Member States with a margin of discretion in relation to the requirement of documents and evidence aimed at identifying the land at issue. This margin of discretion of the Member States also covers the rules related to the evidence to be submitted by the agricultural producer, as well as documents certifying legal title.³⁴ It should be emphasized that in this area, restrictions also apply to the Member States' margin of discretion.³⁵

The relevant EU regulations, that is, the regulations on subsidies,³⁶ and on the protection of the financial interests of the EU,³⁷ set forth the limits of the exercise of the margin of discretion of the Member States: according to the former, the decision-making of the member states can only be conducted

²⁴ *ibid.* paragraphs 62-64.

²⁵ *ibid.* paragraphs 69-70.

²⁶ It should be noted that the Commission clearly takes a position in favour of strict sanctions in similar procedures, thus, the Commission's position can be considered exceptional in this respect.

²⁷ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-375/08, paragraph 72.

²⁸ As regards the provisions on the sanctions, the CJEU made reference to the judgments rendered in the National Farmers' Union (C-354/95), the Schilling (C-63/00), and the Greken (C-295/02) cases. In those judgements, the CJEU examined sanctions set forth directly in secondary EU acts.

²⁹ *ibid.* paragraphs 74-76.

³⁰ *ibid.* paragraph 77.

³¹ *ibid.* paragraph 78.

³² Regulation 2419/2001 and Recital 48 thereof.

³³ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-375/08, paragraph 79-81.

³⁴ *ibid.* paragraph 82.

³⁵ *ibid.* paragraph 83.

³⁶ Recital (15) of Regulation 1254/1999.

³⁷ Article 8(1) and 8(2) of Regulation 2988/95.

on the basis of objective criteria, in the framework of which, inter alia, the principle of equal treatment must be observed, and market and competition distortions must be avoided.³⁸ The acting national courts must also examine whether the obligation to present the legal title applies to all applicants.³⁹

The latter, that is, the regulation on the protection of the financial interests of the Union,⁴⁰ requires that the measures introduced in order to ensure the regularity and reality of transactions that affect the financial interests of the EU must be proportionate to the objectives pursued and appropriate to the specific nature of each sector.⁴¹

Summarizing the above findings, the EU court stated that the exercise by Member States of their discretion in respect of the evidence to be provided in support of an aid application,⁴² particularly the mandatory rules of the Member States regarding the submission of the legal title, “must be consistent with the objectives pursued by the Community legislation concerned, as well as the general principles of Community law and, in particular, the principle of proportionality”.

The Court of Justice of the European Union clarified⁴³ that when applying the relevant provisions of the EU law and the provisions of the integrated administration and control system, the EU and Member State legislature, as well as the acting national courts, must bear in mind the principle of proportionality in the application of the applied measures so that those do not exceed the extent necessary to achieve the objectives pursued and that the introduced measures are suitable for achieving those objectives.⁴⁴

The proper and effective implementation of the EU provisions regarding the operation of the Common Agricultural Policy and the integrated administration and control system, as well as the protection of the financial interests of the EU require the implementation of Member State measures.⁴⁵ The national regulations examined in the main proceedings were aimed at enforcing those. The CJEU added that the Member States' measures also aim to prevent rearers from unlawfully making use of land belonging to others by circumventing EU legislation, and found that the requirement of a valid legal title seems proportional to the realization of this goal.⁴⁶

³⁸ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-375/08, paragraph 84.

³⁹ *ibid.*

⁴⁰ *ibid.* paragraph 85.

⁴¹ *ibid.*

⁴² *ibid.* paragraph 86.

⁴³ The Court referred to the judgment rendered in the *Viamex Agrar Handel* case (C-37/06) as an example of the application of the principle of proportionality. In the main proceedings, in the area of export refunds for agricultural products, the member state authority refused a payment, because the maximum delivery time limit specified in the annex of the relevant EU directive was exceeded by more than one day. There was also a dispute as to whether the maximum delivery time limit applies not only to road but also to rail transport. In the interpretation of the CJEU, the time limit in question also applies to rail transports, however, two cases must be clearly distinguished from each other: if animals die as a result of a violation of the provisions of the directive, the EU legislature leaves no room for discretion to the Member States, and the subsidy cannot be paid. On the other hand, in cases where the violation of the directive does not lead to the death of animals, the EU legislature provides a margin of discretion: Member States may reject the full export refund or may reduce or maintain the subsidies in question.

⁴⁴ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-375/08, paragraph 87.

⁴⁵ *ibid.* paragraph 88.

⁴⁶ *ibid.*

The CJEU certainly does not have comprehensive knowledge of the circumstances of the main proceedings, therefore it "emphasized" that despite the fact that the examined Member State regulations meet the objectives set by EU law and the criteria established by the principle of proportionality, the national court must examine, whether, inter alia,⁴⁷ the principle of proportionality⁴⁸ was in fact observed, taking into account the unique characteristics of the case.

4. Decision Kfv.IV.35.319/2013/3 of the Curia

The Curia rendered its decision in a legal dispute concerning the withdrawal of support related to a payment from the Common Agricultural Policy, in which the concerned agricultural producer, inter alia, maintained that the additional condition imposed on him by the legislation of the Member State as a condition for awarding the support at issue was not included in the relevant EU regulation, consequently, it is incompatible with EU law.

In its decision, the Curia does not dispute that Regulation (EC) 73/2009 does not set forth a direct obligation that requires proof of the legality of possession (availability) supported by a deed in relation to the parcel affected by the subsidy application as a condition for the use of the subsidies at issue. The EU regulation only stipulates that the land in question is to be available to the agricultural producer concerned.

The Curia examined the margin of discretion provided by Regulation (EC) 73/2009, in the course of which it took into account, inter alia, the increase in the efficiency of inspections among the objectives pursued by the preamble of the regulation. In addition, the Curia also considered Regulation (EC) 1290/2005, which, in order to protect the financial interests of the EU, requires the Member States to take all measures necessary, inter alia, to prevent and sanction irregularities.

The "Community legal objectives and the normative rules binding the Member States", which were taken into account during the examination, convinced the Curia that the Member States have a margin of discretion to implement additional conditions that provide additional guarantees beyond those set forth in the regulation on the use of subsidies in order to protect the financial interests of the EU. The Court found that such a guarantee is provided by the documentation that proves the legality of the ownership of the given parcel.

With regard to the judgment of the CJEU rendered in the Pontini case, the Curia examined the legislation disputed in the given procedure in terms of whether the additional conditions of the Member States in question meet the criteria implied in the general principles of EU law, that is, whether they are discriminatory in nature, and whether compliance with imposes a disproportionate burden on agricultural producers. Pursuant to the relevant Hungarian legislation, the lawfulness of the land use is proved by a certificate from the land use register or other documentary evidence that is suitable for verifying the legal title of possession. For example, such completely substantiating document can be a contract concluded in compliance with the formalities applicable to land use.

⁴⁷ In paragraph 90 of the Pontini judgement, the CJEU points out the observation of the general rules of the EU law, with particular emphasis on the principle of proportionality within that category.

⁴⁸ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-375/08, paragraph 89.

In the interpretation of the Curia, as an additional condition for obtaining EU and member state budget funds, the documentary proof contributes to a more effective traceability of the use of funds, and is therefore considered a necessary additional condition according to an objective assessment.

According to the Curia, the weight of the condition added by the Member State is relativized by the fact that the additional condition imposed by the relevant internal legal regulations can be fulfilled by the agricultural producer with a contract concluded in compliance with the appropriate formalities, and that obtaining data from the land use register – required as a general rule – which is accessible to anyone, cannot be considered a disproportionate burden.

The condition added by the Member State applies to all agricultural producers who apply for single area payment, so in the interpretation of the Court, it is not considered discriminatory either.

5. The role of OLAF reports – the order rendered in the Inox Mare SRL case⁴⁹

The said order of the General Court points out the obligations of the Member States in relation to OLAF reports, with particular regard to the national courts. The legal entity concerned by the main proceedings was an capital company incorporated under Italian law which, inter alia, imported stainless steel products into the European Union.

OLAF issued a report against the economic operator concerned, in which it requested the Italian authorities to impose appropriate measures. The report established that the products marketed by the economic operator were subject to customs and anti-dumping measures. The products in question actually originate from Taiwan, yet they were listed as products from the Philippines subject to a preferential tariff.

By his application, the economic operator asked the General Court to annul the acts of OLAF aimed against him. The European Commission, on the other hand, maintained that the referred acts cannot be the subject of annulment proceedings, as final OLAF reports and recommendations do not have binding legal effects.

According to the established case-law, within the framework of the annulment procedure, only legal acts or decisions can be challenged that have binding legal effects in terms of the plaintiff, and affect the plaintiff's interests, causing a significant change in its legal situation.⁵⁰

The EU case-law related to Regulation (EC) 1073/199 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the investigations conducted by OLAF has concluded that the reports produced as a result of external and internal investigations carried out by OLAF do not significantly modify the situation of

⁴⁹ Order of the General Court, T-289/16.

⁵⁰ Court of Justice of the European Union, C-362/08.

the persons indicated in the report.⁵¹ In the interpretation of the General Court,⁵² the final nature of the OLAF report does not confer⁵³ the character of an act with binding legal effect.⁵⁴

It should also be noted that in the concerned area, that is, in the field of EU material customs law, *inter alia*, the making of decisions on the subsequent payment of uncollected customs duties falls under the jurisdiction of the Member States based on the case-law of the General Court,⁵⁵ and they have a margin of discretion regarding the requests of economic operators for the repayment or remission of import customs to take into account the unique⁵⁶ and factual characteristics of each actor.⁵⁷

The General Court recalled its settled case-law, according to which⁵⁸ the Member State authorities must make a decision regarding what measures to take following OLAF's recommendations: it follows that all the guarantees provided by Member State law must be ensured in relation to such procedures, as well as those guarantees, which follow from the general principles of EU law.⁵⁹ The General Court reminded that the courts of the Member States may, or should, refer to the CJEU in the preliminary ruling procedure.⁶⁰

The plaintiff in the case also relied on the alleged violation by OLAF of his right to adversarial proceedings and evidence, as well as his right to effective judicial protection against illegal investigative acts. According to case-law, the invoked irregularities cannot attribute the nature of an act causing damage to the report in an action for annulment, since such violations can only be contested as support for a claim directed against a later, challengeable act to the extent that they influenced its content.⁶¹

The General Court reminded that the solution used in the order rendered in the case *Planet v. Commission*⁶² invoked by the plaintiff cannot be applied to the present case, since in the cited case the act of OLAF caused a significant change in the legal entity's situation.

The EU case-law regarding OLAF reports seems clear in that no actual legal binding force is conferred to them against the persons indicated in them, that is, they do not seem to significantly modify the legal situation of those persons. It should be noted that, in practice, the possibility cannot be ruled out

⁵¹ Judgement of the General Court, T-309/03, and T-690/13.

⁵² Judgement of the General Court, T-309/03, paragraph 49.

⁵³. There is no doubt that EU courts have a monopoly on the authentic interpretation of EU law, that is, it is indisputable that, according to case-law, a final OLAF report cannot be the subject of an action for annulment. However, this does not rule out the possibility that, in practice, the final OLAF may still have a decisive effect on the legal status of the persons concerned, particularly if the acting national courts do not comply with the guarantees established in the case-law. This issue will be explained in detail below.

⁵⁴ It is worth to be considered in more detail.

⁵⁵ Judgement of the General Court, T-576/11.

⁵⁶ However, in our opinion, the fact that the Member State authorities are competent to decide these issues and have a certain margin of discretion, does not mean that they are exempt from ensuring the protection of the financial interests of the EU in this field, and that they have no obligation to take appropriate measures against offences affecting the EU budget.

⁵⁷ Judgement of the General Court, T-249/12.

⁵⁸ Judgement of the General Court, T-289/16, paragraph 40.

⁵⁹ The General Court adds that the requirements arising from the general principles of EU law must be taken into account if the Member States implement EU law.

⁶⁰ Judgement of the General Court, T-289/16, paragraph 40.

⁶¹ Judgement of the General Court, T-309/03.

⁶² Judgement of the General Court, T-320/09.

that an OLAF report will eventually have such an impact on the national case-law that it actually leads to changes in the legal situation of the person concerned.

From another aspect, it should be mentioned that in the field of payments under the Common Agricultural Policy, as is evident from the case-law,⁶³ OLAF plays a significant role⁶⁴ in the detection of possible offences and, in particular, in the imposition of sanctions with financial consequences against the Member States.

This fact can actually encourage the authorities of the Member States to largely comply with the contents of OLAF's reports and recommendations. In practice, it cannot be ruled out that a possible OLAF report will be considered by the authorities and courts of the Member States in accordance with the requirements of EU law. It is true that it follows from Article 9 and Recital (13) of Regulation 1073/1999 that the final findings of OLAF's reports do not automatically result in proceedings against the persons concerned, as the Member State authorities are free to decide on the measures to be taken. In its judgment rendered in the *Tillack v. Commission* case, inter alia, the General Court confirmed that it is the sole responsibility of the Member State authorities to decide what measures they take⁶⁵ based on the information sent by OLAF.⁶⁶

The General Court pointed out that,⁶⁷ in line with Article 11(2) of Regulation (EU) 883/2013, OLAF reports actually constitute admissible evidence in administrative or judicial proceedings of the Member State⁶⁸ and is subject to the evaluation rules set forth in national legislation. However, Article 11 (3) of the above regulation does not attribute to the OLAF report an obligation on the basis of which the Member State authorities should adopt measures, and in the interpretation of the General Court, based on the wording of the Regulation, the obligation prescribed by Article 11 (6), according to which the Member State authorities are obliged to inform OLAF about the measures taken, cannot be considered an obligation but should be interpreted⁶⁹ as a possibility.⁷⁰

The General Court recalled that in the case of proceedings initiated before a national court, the legal protection guaranteed by all internal laws must be ensured, as well as the guarantees provided by the general principles of EU law.⁷¹ The General Court reminded that the acting national court not only has the opportunity, but also, where appropriate, the obligation to refer questions to the CJEU for preliminary ruling.⁷²

⁶³ Judgement of the General Court, T-267/07.

⁶⁴ It should be emphasized, however, that fact that OLAF plays or may play a prominent role in the imposition of possible financial sanctions against Member States does not mean that OLAF reports are legally binding on the persons concerned.

⁶⁵ Judgement of the General Court, T-193/04

⁶⁶ It should be noted that the aforesaid principles did not change even in terms of Regulation (EU) 883/2013 repealing Regulation (EC) 1073/1999 and Council Regulation (Euratom) 1074/1999.

⁶⁷ Judgement of the General Court, T-289/16, paragraph 20.

⁶⁸ Maria Fartunova: *La preuve dans le droit de l'Union européenne*, Bruylant, Bruxelles, 2013, Maria Fartunova explains that the original version of the treaties did not include provisions regarding evidence. Secondary EU acts have begun to deal with evidence in certain fields, in order to assert the subjective rights of legal entities.

⁶⁹ It should also be noted that the individual language versions differed as to whether Member States should take mandatory measures.

⁷⁰ *ibid.* paragraph 21.

⁷¹ Judgement of the General Court, T-289/16, paragraph 40.

⁷² *ibid.*

A. An example of the case

In 2010, an agricultural producer in Hungary⁷³ was awarded a tender issued by the Ministry of Defense for the lease of land located within the security zone of military areas for the purpose of sheep grazing. In the spring of the same year, the Ministry of Defense notified the concerned agricultural producer of the positive decision as regards the awarding of the tender. The land at issue was handed over to the agricultural producer in the spring of the same year. For the agricultural producer to be able to submit the area payment application based on the relevant Hungarian legislation, it would have been necessary to conclude a lease agreement signed in compliance with the appropriate formalities. However, the contract lacked the signature of the Minister of National Defense until August of the same year. The agricultural producer submitted his payment application before the minister signed the contract.

When submitting the subsidy application, agricultural producer was required to declare, inter alia, that he has a land use deed or a valid lease agreement concluded in compliance with the appropriate formalities at the time of submitting the subsidy application. It is undisputed that at the time of submitting the subsidy application, the agricultural producer did not have a valid lease contract concluded in compliance with the appropriate formalities in line with Hungarian law. Yet, it was not contested in the legal dispute that the land in question was handed over to the agricultural producer, who grazed sheep on the land concerned, that is, carried out agricultural activities.

The authorities initially accepted the subsidy application submitted by the agricultural producer, then revoked this decision and demanded the repayment of the subsidy amounts. The authorities initiated criminal proceedings. OLAF issued a report in which it found that the agricultural producer received the subsidies at issue unlawfully. In its report, OLAF did not substantiate its finding that the fraud was threatening the financial interests of the European Union with legal but rather factual arguments, for example, that the distance of the agricultural producer's seat from the given area does not make the conduct of actual agricultural activity conceivable. In the end, the court imposed against the agricultural producer, inter alia, imprisonment to be served. The agricultural producer disputed whether it is lawful under EU law to require a lease agreement concluded with appropriate formalities. The court acting in the final instance did not take into account the above arguments and did not refer the question to the Court of Justice of the European Union within the framework of the preliminary ruling procedure. This court considered that the judgment of the CJEU rendered in the Pontini case adequately supports the fact that a Member State may demand a contract signed in compliance with the appropriate formalities.

B. Assessment

The question of whether the agricultural producer had a contract concluded in compliance with the appropriate formalities⁷⁴ required by the relevant Hungarian legislation at the time of the submission of the subsidy must be decided solely on the basis of national law. On the other hand, in the event of sanctions imposed by court, particularly criminal sanctions, EU law must be or should have been taken into account.

⁷³ For privacy reasons, as well as other aspects, we do not consider it important to provide a detailed description of the circumstances of the case.

⁷⁴ Or, in the absence of that, with other requirements.

One of the most important arguments presented by the agricultural producer was based on the judgment of the CJEU rendered in the Pontini case, according to which the subsidies at issue must be judged on the basis of the size of the land available to the agricultural producer and the number of animals kept on it, that is, the actual utilization. As a result, the question should not have been decided on the basis of a document related to the title required by a Member State or exclusively defined in internal law, but the criteria defined by EU law should have been taken into account primarily.

In its judgment rendered in the Pontini case, the CJEU indeed admitted that the relevant EU regulations oblige the Member States to ensure the effectiveness of the support system, so requiring legal title seems to be a suitable tool for preventing offences. However, based on the case-law of the CJEU, Member State legislation must be consistent with the criteria established by the general principles of EU law, with particular regard to the principle of proportionality.

As mentioned above, the Curia "adopted" the judgement rendered in the Pontini case into Hungarian law, and the Hungarian courts and administrative bodies followed the Curia's interpretation. In our view, the Curia properly examined the consistency of the relevant legislation⁷⁵ on Hungarian legal title with the general principles and other requirements of EU law, however, it conspicuously failed to mention the obligation set forth in the Pontini case, that the acting national courts must examine their decisions taking into account the unique circumstances of the cases from the aspect of the general principles of EU law.⁷⁶

Following the position of the Curia in the Pontini case, the court that imposed the imprisonment to be served⁷⁷ in the case omitted the examination related to the general principles of EU law in light of the unique circumstances of the case. In its judgment, the court found that the agricultural producer submitted his subsidy application ignoring the conditions set by the Hungarian legislature, that is, in the absence of a contract signed by both parties,⁷⁸ thereby committing the felony of budget fraud.

In this paper, we do not intend to examine the court's decision from the aspect of Hungarian law, although it is difficult to dispute that the agricultural producer did not have the conditions required by Hungarian legislation at the time of submitting the subsidy application.

Based on the judgment in the Pontini case, subsidies must be judged on the basis of the actual use and the area available to the agricultural producer, and not on the basis of the title document required by the national legislation. In addition to examining the legislation related to the legal title to be introduced by the Member State, the case-law of the CJEU requires that the acting national court take into

⁷⁵ It is telling that the Court examined the requirements defined by the principle of equal treatment as whether the Hungarian legislation in question applies to all producers. However, the principle of equal treatment is authoritative precisely with regard to the examination of individual circumstances. An example of this is the judgment of the CJEU rendered in the Szatmári Malom case.

⁷⁶ As already mentioned, it cannot be considered a unique Hungarian characteristic that the national courts ignore the general principles.

⁷⁷ We primarily examine the decision of the court that imposed the imprisonment. In that regard, the imposition of a financial sanction is less relevant. It should be noted that the principle of proportionality should have been applied in this regard as well.

⁷⁸ As we have already mentioned, the minister had not yet signed the contract at the time of submitting the grant application, it happened at a later date.

account the unique circumstances of the legal dispute and the requirements defined by the general principles of EU law in its decision.

We believe that in this respect the criteria defined by the general principles of proportionality and equal treatment should have been taken into account. The principle of proportionality requires that the measures used do not extend what is necessary to achieve the objective pursued.

The question arises whether, with regard to the requirements related to the general principle of EU law, that is, the principle of proportionality, the criminal sanction applied in this case, that is, the imposition of imprisonment, must be or should have been assessed by the acting national court from the aspect of preventing fraud that affect the financial interests of the EU or the effectiveness of the payment under the CAP, or from the aspect of the failure to comply with the legislation related to legal title. Based on the judgment rendered in the Pontini case, the criteria of EU law must be clearly applied, and not the implementation measures of the Member States.

Following this interpretation, the damage to the Union's financial interests or the effectiveness of the payments cannot really be substantiated, if the agricultural producer had the land in question, where they carried out agricultural activities, at their disposal. A criminal sanction imposed by ignoring the criteria set by EU law seriously violates the requirements set by the principle of proportionality.

The principle of equal treatment requires that comparable situations be treated the same and different situations differently.⁷⁹ In the application of this principle, attention should have been paid to the fact that the agricultural producer had at his disposal the given land where he carried out agricultural activities, the producer won the tender for the lease of the area, and the signing of the final contract was delayed through no fault of his own. This argument is supported by the fact that later the minister also signed the contract for the use of the area. In other words, the requirements defined on the basis of the principle of equal treatment are clearly violated if similar criminal sanctions are imposed on an agricultural producer who does not carry out agricultural activities in the given area, or who, acting in bad faith, clearly does not have any legal title to use the concerned land.

In the above, the application of the principle of proportionality and equal treatment can be linked to the case-law established in the scope of application of CAP. As opposed to this special case, EU law also requires, or should have required, that the acting national court take into account the requirements defined by the general principles mentioned above in a "general case". Based on established case-law, if the Member State imposes sanctions within the scope of application of a secondary EU legal act, it must do so on the basis of criteria defined by the general principles of EU law.

The court's decision may have been influenced by the OLAF report, which may have given the impression that the EU law itself requires the imposition of the criminal sanctions at issue. According to the practice of the CJEU, as we examined above, OLAF's recommendations and final reports are not legally binding legal acts. Following such a report, it is for the Member State authorities to decide what measures they will take. OLAF reports are in fact qualify as evidence that is subject to the evaluation rules set forth in Member State procedural law. The acting national courts are not only entitled, but also obliged to refer to the CJEU in this area.

⁷⁹ The principle of equal treatment was confirmed several times by the CJEU in the scope of the application of the CAP. See the judgement rendered in the Szatmári Malom case (C-135/13).

It cannot be ruled out that the national courts considered the fact that the European Commission takes OLAF's reports into account when it obliges the Member States to bear financial consequences, inter alia, within the scope of application of the CAP.

The consideration of general principles may have been hindered by the perception that the field of criminal law is traditionally classified as an area of national sovereignty,⁸⁰ where it is difficult to accept the application of EU law in the absence of explicit secondary EU legal acts.

The national courts have difficulties accepting the application of the general principles against legislation, and in such cases, they rarely turn to the Court of Justice of the European Union.

6. Summary

In relation to the subsidies to be provided in the field of the Common Agricultural Policy, that is, the positive form of integration, which constitutes a significant part of the European Union's budget, the relevant legislation prioritizes the prevention of offences. In many cases, the case-law of the CJEU emphasizes the protection of the financial interests of the EU over general principles protecting economic actors. In addition, the European Commission, along with OLAF, acts strictly against the Member States.⁸¹

The general principles of EU law, on the other hand, play a major role in the case of so-called atypical or irregular regulations. However, the case-law of the CJEU in this area is difficult to integrate into the practice of the Member State authorities and the case-law of the national courts.

In this respect as well, the case-law developed in the Pontini case forms a separate, somewhat special category: the Member States do have implementation powers and even obligations to adopt legislation to ensure the prevention of offences. However, the general principles of EU law provide a two-fold control regarding the national implementation measures in this area. The requirements imposed by the general principles of EU law must be met, on the one hand, by the legislation of the Member States, and, on the other hand, by the decisions made in individual cases.

National courts have significant difficulties applying the general principles of EU law, and this is related to the fact that in many cases the national courts do not comply with their obligation to refer questions to the CJEU in the framework of preliminary ruling.⁸²

The issue is further complicated by the fact that, based on the case-law of the CJEU, the OLAF reports do not entail a legal obligation for the Member States to initiate proceedings against the person concerned, nonetheless, within the scope of application of the CAP, the Commission, in cooperation with

⁸⁰ Perrine Simon explains that, despite Article 83 of the TFEU, the EU's competences in the field of criminal law can still be considered uncertain. In any case, in this area the principles of proportionality and subsidiarity are applied most often. Perrine Simon: *La compétence d'incrimination de L'Union européenne*, Bruylant, Bruxelles, 2019.

⁸¹ See footnote 65.

⁸² As Laurent Coutron explains the problem that there is nothing to be done with national courts that mistakenly or deliberately do not comply with their obligations to request a preliminary ruling procedure, has been a longstanding problem, in *L'obligation de renvoi préjudiciel à la Cour de justice: une obligation sanctionnée? sous la dir. de Laurent Coutron, Bruylant, Bruxelles, 2014.*

OLAF, imposes financial sanctions on the Member States if they fail to act properly against financial offences.

Similar cases could be prevented in the future by taking into account the case-law of the CJEU in the scope of application of the CAP and the general principles, as well as if, in case of uncertainty, the national courts would not hesitate to turn to the CJEU.

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